

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15276462

Parenting Styles, A Prevailing Factor To The Social And Moral Decadence Of Our Society

Dr. Mrs. Ayibatari Blessed Enekeme

**Department of Counselling And Educational Psychology
Faculty of Education
Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State, Nigeria**

ABSTRACT

In every society, the home is a place that has the responsibility of raising children responsibly to the betterment of their immediate and larger society. These children when they are being properly raised will bring joy and fulfillment to themselves and to the larger society in general. Where parents within the family circle bring up their children morally with the proper parental style, children will be well adjusted and uphold society values, this will in turn create a harmonious society where peace love and joy reigns. However, the reverse will be the case if proper parenting is not given to our up strings, unhealthy life styles like; promiscuity, drug addition, cultism, rape, assassination, banditry, terrorism, armed robbery and other vices may ensue. Society today has been swallowed up by some of these societal vices. It is based on this premise that this paper is out to X-ray the different parenting styles that can be best for our children and wards today so that society can be a well secured and a better place to live in. It also gave some recommendations like; the child should be part of decisions any decisions that concerns him especially the teenagers Children should be showed love and affection. Children should be disciplined when necessary. Etc.

Keywords: Parenting, Styles, Moral and Social Decadence.

INTRODUCTION

The proper upbringing of a child depends on the type of parenting style given to the child at home and the family which is the first agent of socialization. Where a home or family adopts a good parenting style the better for the social and moral growth and development of that child or ward. The reverse could be detrimental to the child, and his/her immediate and the society at large. Parenting is the task of parents in bringing up their children. It is the main task of parents that provide care for a child or children. Virasiri, Yunibhand and Chaiyawai (2011). Hoghughi & Long Defines Parenting as a positive purposive and nurturing activity which is specifically aimed at promoting a child as welfare or ensuring the survival and development of children. Hendricks (2025) defined parenting as the process of raising children and providing them with protection and care in order to ensure their healthy development into adulthood.

PARENTING STYLES

Baumrind (1967) is of the view that the ways in which parents rear children can have lifelong impact on children's development. Baumrind in Lerzelere, Sheffield, & Harrist (2013) asserted that parenting styles have been found to predict child wellbeing in the domains of social competence, academic performance, psychological development and problem behaviour. Thus in 1960, she identified three main styles of parenting Authoritarian, Authoritative and Permissive and later a fourth style neglectful. Sanvictores and Mendez (2022) also highlighted parenting styles as follows;

- i. **Authoritarian Parenting:** Authoritarian Parents engages in a one-way mode of communication where they have strict rules that the children are expected to obey without questions or negotiation. The rules are rarely explained and children are expected to meet up with these rules without making mistakes. Errors are often met with punishment. Parents tend to be less flexible here. For instance, in an authoritarian parenting style children eat the same meal as everyone else or finish everything on their plate. The Family is unlikely to discuss why they eat certain foods. According to them children raised by authoritarian parents often exhibit well behaviour due to the consequences of misbehavior. However, children from the parenting style can have level of aggression, shyness, social ineptitude and difficult in making their own decisions. Strict parental rules and punishment can also make children to rebel against authorities as they grow older.
- ii. **Permissive Parenting:** Permissive Parenting are typically warm and nurturing. They have minimized expectation, from their children. They implore few rules and maintain open communication. They allow their children to operate independently. They met out frequent disciplinary actions. Children with the type of parenting styles can enjoy considerable freedom in making decisions like eating habits, no specific time for bed time etc.
- iii. **The Authoritative Parenting:** Here Parents have high level of responsiveness and demandingness. Parent are supportive, warm and attentive. They also have clear expectations and boundaries and encourage independence within limits.
- iv. **Uninvolved Parenting:** This type, grants children a high level of freedom. No specific disciplinary rule is given to the children. Parents detach themselves emotionally from their children. However, they may fulfil the child's basic need. Children from this type of home may develop resilience and may be more self-sufficient. However, there may be problems of emotional reputation, they may face academic challenges, not being able to maintain social relationship etc.

In recent times Koblin (2021) has the 5th Parenting Style. According to him there are four widely researched parenting styles, which are; **authoritative, permissive, authoritarian, neglectful and the fifth one is over involved parents.** Parents in this type of parenting style hover about and micro manage every aspect of their children. They are also known as (snow plows). Children of this home can't do anything alone. They can't handle challenges alone. They lack perseverance.

Studies have overtime showed that the Authoritative parenting style is the best. Parents should set rules for their children and encourage them to carry it out. They shouldn't be too Autocratic and rigid; children tend to be aggressive and erratic later in live. (Koblin 2021). The permissive parenting style itself does not set any rule or control over their children. Neglecting Parents are uninvolved and uninterested in whatever the child does. Children that are not given proper control, can be loose. Such children can become wayward and indiscipline because Parents don't care about their misbehavior. The children can come home late in the night, join bad group in the community, drop out of school without the parents knowing. Since there has been no standard of check mating their behaviour from childhood, setting discipline at teenage age will become apparently difficult. Children are no longer being properly disciplined these days. The religious book teaches us that we should not spare the rod to spoil the child. What then do we find today, most of our children cannot be corrected at home or at school. Gone are those traditional good old days where the child belongs to everybody in the society and can be corrected by anybody. The case is different today, one does not touch another person's child. The teacher in school cannot even dare it. Our core values of respect for elders, reverence for human lives and properly, dignity in labour, sexual morality etc. are grading eroding away. Our society is today threatened with assassinations, armed robbery, banditry, cybercrime, human and child trafficking, drug addiction, rape, examination malpractice, corruption etc. All these can be traced to bad parenting styles.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Parents should start early in training their children and wards. The religious books say train up a child in the way he should go when he is old, he will not depart from it. Ensure your child goes along with you to your place of worship. Teach him/her the tenants of your faith. Thus he/she will be brought up morally and become a good citizen to himself/herself in the nearest future.
2. Love your children and discipline your child. The good books also say do not spare the rod to spoil the child. In disciplining the child, don't do it in anger but in an atmosphere of love.
3. Require obedience from your children. Don't overindulge them. Ensure they obey the rules and regulations of the family. Sometimes allow them make mistakes (not the grievous ones though) and let them correct themselves.
4. Teach them the Holy word of God at home and in the school. By so doing they will know that crimes like killing, is against man and God.
5. Modelling is of paramount importance. As parents be a good model of good behaviour for them to emulate.
6. Respect and honour for one another is also paramount. When we respect our fellow human beings committing havoc will be quite un thinkable, abnormal and morally unjustifiable.
7. Counselling parents and children with abnormal behaviour is paramount.
8. Counsellors can give orientation during P.T.A Meetings in schools, on good parenting styles.
9. Orientation programs by counsellors can also be done in the media.
10. The teaching of our religious studies should effectively be reinstated in our curriculum. Prayers should be allowed in schools. This will create the fear of God more in the lives of the children, in our homes, schools and society, at large. This will in turn reduce societal and moral decadence in our society.
11. Children should be sometimes allowed to be part of decisions that concerns them.

CONCLUSION

The paper X-rayed, parenting styles as a prevailing factor to the Social and moral decadence of society. Different types of parenting styles were examined. The family parenting styles should be revisited in a way of creating caution against evil and waywardness in our society.

REFERENCES

- Baumrind, D (1967) Child Care Practices anteceding three patterns of pre-school behaviour *Genetic Psychology Monographs*. 75 (1), 43-58
- Hendricks, M. K (2025) Parenting Psychology of mental Health <https://www.britannica.com/poid-parenting>. Retrieved April 21st by 12:42
- The Unschooler's Educational Dictionary. The Guide to models of Alternative Education <https://sproutschools.com>. retrieved. April 21st 2025, 3:27pm.
- Lerzeler, R. E, Sheffield, A. & Harriot, A.W (2013) *Authoritative Parenting Synthesize nurturance and discipline for optimal child development*. Washington, DC. American Psychological Association.
- San Viclores I. T & Mendez, M. D (2025) *Types of parenting styles and effects on children*. London. Star Pearls Publishing etc.
- Virasiri, S, Yunibhand, J & Chaiyawat C, (2011) Parenting what are the critical attributes. *Journal of the medical association of Thailand* 94(9) 1109 - 1116